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**IMPACT OF AGILE LEADERSHIP, INFORMATION SYSTEM, AND
EMPOWERMENT ON THE ORGANIZATIONAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN
THE ZAIN TELECOMMUNICATION COMPANY**

敏捷領導力、信息系統和授權對贊恩電信公司組織企業家精神的影響

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Abstract

The main goal of this study is to examine how empowerment, information systems, and agile leadership affect organizational entrepreneurship in the Zain telecommunications company. After the sample-checking procedure, 223 samples were collected. The research investigation processed all the data gathered using the PLS program. The research's conclusions show several connections and interconnections that may impact improving organizational entrepreneurship. The study findings show that agile leadership, including inclusive leadership, shared accountability, and collaborative decision-making has a favorable direct impact on entrepreneurship. The outcome indicated that information systems, including system flexibility, shared information and reports, authorization, speed, and enterprise computing, benefit entrepreneurship. The outcome also demonstrated that empowerment has direct and advantageous effects on entrepreneurship, including certifications relating to quality, rejection rates, past performance, and competence. There was a discrepancy between the research findings and those of other studies, which found no connection between the factors and e-learning satisfaction and entrepreneurship. This study suggests that for businesses to deal with information systems effectively, keep up with change and competition, gain more competitive advantages, develop new knowledge, and support and enhance the decision-making process, they must begin the process of entrepreneurship for all business

transactional processes, documents, and orders. The uniqueness of this study creates a framework for emphasizing the essential contributions that an information system, an empowered workforce, and agile leadership can make to foster organizational entrepreneurship.

Keywords: Agile Leadership, Information System, Empowerment, E-Learning Satisfaction, Entrepreneurship

摘要 本研究的主要目標是研究授權、信息系統和敏捷領導力如何影響贊因電信公司的組織創業精神。在樣本檢查程序之後，收集了223個樣本。研究調查處理了使用偏最小二乘法程序收集的所有數據。該研究的結論顯示了可能影響改善組織企業家精神的幾種聯繫和相互聯繫。研究結果表明，敏捷領導力，包括包容性領導力、共同問責制和協作決策制定，對創業具有有利的直接影響。結果表明，信息系統，包括系統靈活性、共享信息和報告、授權、速度和企業計算，有利於創業。結果還表明，授權對創業有直接和有利的影響，包括與質量、拒絕率、過去的表演和能力有關的認證。研究結果與其他研究結果存在差異，其他研究發現這些因素與電子學習滿意度和創業精神之間沒有聯繫。這項研究表明，企業要有效地處理信息系統、跟上變化和競爭、獲得更多競爭優勢、開發新知識以及支持和加強決策過程，他們必須開始所有業務交易的創業過程流程、文檔和訂單。這項研究的獨特性創建了一個框架，用於強調信息系統、賦權的勞動力和敏捷領導力可以為培養組織企業家精神做出的重要貢獻。

关键词: 敏捷領導力、信息系統、授權、電子學習滿意度, 創業精神

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently, the study of strategic information systems has noticed an increase in the concept of entrepreneurship [1], [2], and [3]. To develop strategies that can effectively drive operational performance, businesses have attempted to create novel solutions at the organizational level by using knowledge [4]. Several new studies must define the capabilities and characteristics of entrepreneurship, as well as its capacity to help organizations improve their operational performance and provide customers with what they want. The phenomenon of entrepreneurship is a recent phenomenon with various levels and characteristics [2]. Entrepreneurship is the capacity to take charge of an organization and manage its business operations while navigating any risks, issues, or uncertainties to maximize profits [3]. It is crucial for an organization to recognize the need for change. The rapid evolution of an organization's characteristics drives a firm to improve the technological systems it uses, develop new ideas and products, find creative solutions, run operations through technological systems, and boost performance efficiency and effectiveness [1].

We provide an inductive framework that describes the impact of Agility system, information system, and empowerment systems on entrepreneurship by focusing on the usage of e-learning satisfaction. This framework is based

on our research of the literature reviews and prior studies. The requirement for any business to comprehend and implement the significance of focusing on entrepreneurship and to make it a way of conducting everyday tasks derives from learning the effect of preceding variables and their impact on entrepreneurship. By assisting organizations in defining entrepreneurship metrics, scope, and speed, the research examines the effects of managing agility system, information system, and empowerment system variables capable of enhancing the use of e-learning satisfaction of organizations to achieve business entrepreneurship. The reviews of the research literature, the findings, and the recommendations for the future are covered in the parts that follow.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Agile System

By using project management and software development, firms may provide goods with added value to customers faster using an agility system [5]. Studies show the value of including customers in the creation of products and set their specifications [6]. Thus, using agile leadership as a powerful tool for linking customers with businesses is essential to the process of creativity and innovation [7], [40]. Most studies agreed that constructing strategic plans capable of producing

detailed product development maps is essential for developing administrative, operational, and industrial areas [8]. An iterative approach called the agility system is used to support managers and Quick and effective information use by decision-makers [9]. Any corporation can apply new business models, develop more goods with additional value, increase customer loyalty and have market share and higher competitive advantages by implementing agile leadership [10], [41].

B. Information System

The definition of an information system is the creation of an efficient and innovative work environment that promotes the exchange of explicit and tacit knowledge among employees. Over time, this results in a productive work environment that can be modified and continuously improved by using fresh ideas to solve problems and face risks [11], [43]. Knowing how to extract the value of knowledge from vast and complicated databases gathered from various sources, such as information obtained through e-learning satisfaction methodologies, the Agility system, learning systems, and social networking sites, demonstrates the potential of information systems [12], [45]. Organizations have found that using information systems effectively helps them understand consumer behavior, lower operating expenses, product costs, and running fees [13], [42]. Information systems are tools that businesses use to give customers what they want by fostering an environment of efficiency, effectiveness, and competition [14].

C. Empowerment

Giving employees the authority and capability to enhance their work, develop the quality of products, and cut expenses while relying on consumer feedback without first waiting for management decisions are referred to as empowerment [15]. The value of employee empowerment has become clearer because of changes in the working environment, how managers and employees interact, and the rise in self-assurance and skill levels of employees [16, 39]. The divide between managers and staff has narrowed thanks to empowerment strategies, which have also transformed the traditional managerial role into one that is ideally interactive, informative, and participative [17].

Ownership and management of information systems presented challenges to organizations, and the amount, quality, accuracy, and validity of the data served as a good indicator of these

challenges. As a result, the empowerment strategy became a successful creative tool for identifying new values that can enable firms to be distinctive and different [18], [19], [20]. Due to the difficulty of working today without the extensive use of technological systems, the ability of organizations to deal with and analyze information systems and try extracting new values, and a complex process that forced organizations to use analytical empowerment tools, the process of organizations becoming entrepreneurs is a complex but necessary process [21], [22], [37]. Using all the warehouse data, classifying, and processing it, and then creating new knowledge are all crucial components of entrepreneurship. These steps enable organizations to manage business with a high level of entrepreneurship, adopt and apply novel ideas, support decision-making, address complex and intractable problems, and finally offer customers novel services and products [23].

D. E-Learning Satisfaction and Organizational Entrepreneurship

Most businesses currently view the development of e-learning as both a challenge and an opportunity waiting to be taken advantage of [24]. One of the successful strategy firms have used to cope with large data is the usage of e-learning satisfaction [25], [44]. Some companies have started to employ e-learning satisfaction as a technique to generate new ideas and create business management strategies based on data that was first provided by customers. However, the organizations view the benefits of e-learning as a chance to enhance their own capabilities, manage their business processes, projects, and plans entrepreneurially, and this will help the organization stand out among rival businesses in the competitive market [26], [27], [28], [29]. Produce creative products and managing business processes and projects entrepreneurially based on the usage of e-learning have become the primary goal of most firms [30]. Organizations constantly seek stability and sustainability, and they are aware of the need to have various skills to connect with customers and offer new goods that are both high-quality and affordable [31], [32], and [38]. To possess multiple competitive advantages, most organizations have turned to enhance their capacity to reach full entrepreneurship as a means of doing so. They have also reduced the costs of commercial, operational transactions, and transportation costs, and have completely relied on technological and agile leadership to handle information systems and customer demands [33], [34], [35]. Based on

reviews and prior research, the following research hypotheses are put forth:

H1: The agility system positively impacts satisfaction with e-learning.

H2: An agile system promotes organizational entrepreneurship.

H3: An information system's impact on e-learning satisfaction is favorable.

H4: The use of information systems fosters organizational entrepreneurship.

H5: Empowerment positively influences E-learning satisfaction.

H6: Empowerment influences organizational entrepreneurship favorably.

H7: Organizational entrepreneurship benefits from e-learning.

III. METHODOLOGY

Google Drive was used to develop, create, and disseminate an online research survey with a

five-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, and 5 = Strongly Agree) to evaluate the major study constructs. Additionally, the researchers used the PLS technique to statistically analyze the study hypotheses. The responses of 223 respondents were accepted for use in the analysis process to discuss the study hypotheses after the data from all 300 respondents had been checked and filtered. Finally, the total number of samples obtained was ten times greater than the number of predictors [29].

IV. RESULTS

The reliability test was completed using the values of composite reliability, average variable extracted, and Cronbach's alpha, which should be greater than or equal to 0.50, as shown in the Table 1 [30]. Additionally, Table 1 clearly demonstrates that the model for this research, which is based on the evaluation, is adequate to be ready to move on to discussing the research hypotheses.

Table 1. Research reliability and validity test

Code	Variable	Factor's Loading	VIF
Agility Leadership (AL) (Chronbach's Alpha: 0.652, CR: 0.824, AVE: 0.587)			
AL1	Inclusive Leadership	0.538	1.241
AL2	Shared Accountability	0.699	2.236
AL3	Group Decision Making	0.721	1.264
AL4			
Information System (Chronbach's Alpha: 0.694, CR: 0.825, AVE: 0.706)			
IS1	Flexibility	0.665	1.479
IS2	Shared Information and Reports	0.700	1.242
IS3	Authorization	0.709	1.387
IS4	Speed	0.690	1.168
IS5	Enterprise Computing	0.710	1.163
Empowerment (Chronbach's Alpha: 0.684, CR: 0.780, AVE: 0.721)			
E1	Quality Related Certification	0.786	2.821
E2	Rejection Rate	0.710	1.254
E3	Performance History	0.613	1.458
E4	competence	0.628	1.368
E-learning Satisfaction (Chronbach's Alpha: 0.744, CR: 0.876, AVE: 0.675)			
ES1	Enterprise System	0.815	1.597
ES2	Internal Integration	0.678	2.467
ES3	Integration with Suppliers	0.754	1.793
Organizational Entrepreneurship (Chronbach's Alpha: 0.846, CR: 0.854, AVE: 0.763)			
OE1	Loyalty	0.778	1.321
OE2	Complaints	0.818	1.321
OE3	Warranty Claims	0.752	1.976

Fig. 2. Research Bootstrapping Results

The direct effects and linkages between the research variables are shown in Table 2; all the search hypotheses have been thoroughly accepted.

Table 2: Path Coefficient Test Results

	Research Hypotheses Test	P_Value	Results
H1	Agile Leadership → E-Learning Satisfaction	0.000	Supported
H2	Agile Leadership → Organizational Entrepreneurship	0.016	Supported
H3	Information System → E-Learning Satisfaction	0.001	Supported
H4	Information System → Organizational Entrepreneurship	0.000	Supported
H5	Empowerment → E-Learning Satisfaction	0.002	Supported
H6	Empowerment → Organizational Entrepreneurship	0.000	Supported
H7	E-Learning Satisfaction → Organizational Entrepreneurship	0.004	Supported

V. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

The study's findings demonstrate how agile leadership, encompassing leadership and cooperation, self-organizing teams, successful transitions, complexity, and adaptability, has a favorable direct impact on entrepreneurship. The outcome agrees with findings from earlier investigations. Additionally, this study demonstrates how information systems—including work groups, collaborative environments, knowledge repositories, training, and integration with the workplace—benefit entrepreneurship. This outcome is consistent with findings from earlier research. Additionally, the findings of the study demonstrate that empowerment affects entrepreneurship positively and directly, as well as tools, self-efficacy, self-advocacy, and competence. This outcome is consistent with that of earlier studies. Finally, the research findings contradict other studies that found no relationship between the variables affecting e-learning pleasure and entrepreneurship. The study's findings also indicate that for organizations, businesses, and companies to deal with information systems effectively, keep up with change and competition, gain competitive advantage, acquire new knowledge, and support and develop decision-making skills, they must immediately begin the entrepreneurial process for all business transactional processes, documents, and orders.

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